

EOSC-Nordic cooperation on CTS certification work

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EOSC Nordic key facts

EOSC-Nordic aims to facilitate the coordination of European Open Science

Cloud (EOSC) relevant initiatives within the Nordic and Baltic countries. The project aims to exploit synergies to achieve greater harmonisation at policy and service provisioning across these countries, in compliance with EOSC agreed standards and practices.

- September 2019 - August 2022 (prolonged for 3 months)
- 24 project participants from 10 countries
- Project Coordinator: [NeIC](#) / [NordForsk](#)
- One of five regional INFRAEOSC 5b projects

<https://www.eosc-nordic.eu>

Certification support for data repositories

- Webinars about Core Trust Seal (CTS) certification
- In-person online support meetings with individual repositories
- A total of 8 repositories from Estonia, Lithuania, Finland, Sweden, Norway and Iceland were supported
 - Topic: Social science, music, biodiversity, protein interactions...

World of data repositories is diverse

Traditional data sets

Communities in DataDOI

Humaniora

Medicina

Realia

Socialia

Tallinna Ülikool

Varia

Recently Added

[Sinimajanduse arendamise asukoha valiku kriteeriumid](#)

Martin, Georg (Tartu Ülikool, 2021)

Sinimajandus, mis hõlmab otseselt kõiki ookeanide ja meredega seotud majandustegevusi, annab ELis tööd üle 4 miljonile inimesele ja moodustab 1,3 % ELi SKPst. Traditsioonilised sinimajanduse sektorid, sealhulgas kalandus, ...

BROWSE

Communities & Collections

By Issue Date

Authors

Titles

Subjects

MY ACCOUNT

Login

Register

DISCOVER

Author

Kivirähk, Juhan (46)

Anonymous (28)

Kalmus, Veronika (9)

Citizen science

The screenshot shows the Laji.fi website interface. At the top is a blue navigation bar with the following items: LAJI.FI, Species (with a dropdown arrow), Browse & Search, Contribute, My Notebook, Forum, More, Log In | Sign Up, and a globe icon with EN. Below the navigation bar is the main content area. On the left, there is a section titled "Finnish Biodiversity Information Facility" with a paragraph of text. Below this text are three white buttons with blue icons and text: "Study species ?" (with icons of a plant, a spider, a mouse, and a mushroom), "Browse & Search ?" (with a magnifying glass over a book), and "Submit observations ?" (with a notepad and pen). On the right, there is a "Latest News" section with a list of news items, each with a link, a category tag, and a date. At the bottom right of the page is a small white button with an envelope icon.

LAJI.FI Species ▾ Browse & Search Contribute My Notebook Forum More Log In | Sign Up EN

Finnish Biodiversity Information Facility

The Finnish Biodiversity Information Facility (FinBIF) is an open access data repository for researchers, government and the public. FinBIF consolidates many collections and datasets of living Finland in a single source. Our online portal, laji.fi, allows you to browse, search and download information about all forms of biological life, and to record and share your own observations. FinBIF is committed to the sharing and promotion of open access data.

Study species ?

Browse & Search ?

Submit observations ?

Latest News

- [Fault in Notebook forms Sunday 15.5. f 0.00 to 13.00 \(GMT+3\) / Fel i anteckningsbokformulär](#)
technical 15.05.2022
- [Vikatila 31.3-1.4. \(korjattu\) / Service problem 1.4. \(fixed\)](#)
technical 01.04.2022
- [State-of-the-art bridge from FinBIF to GBIF](#)
release 02.02.2022
- [Vihko kuvien lisäys on rikki \(korjattu\) / Adding images is broken \(fixed\)](#)
technical 07.01.2022
- [Facebook login fixed / inloggning fixad](#)
technical 28.12.2021

[←_previous](#)

✉

Methods & models

QsarDB HOME REPOSITORY GUIDELINES SOFTWARE BLOG

QSAR DataBase

FAIR repository of (Q)SAR/QSPR models for citing and predicting

[Read more about QsarDB](#) [Visit repository](#)

227	524	75	66600	75%
QDB archives	QSAR models	QMRF documents	Chemical structures	FAIR score

Transparent QSARs
Create and upload QDB archive

Cite QSAR data
Link repository with your publication

Explore chemicals
Search from over 66000 structures

Two different roles

Liisi

- DataDOI Repository provider
- Participated in support meetings offered by EOSC Nordic WP4 team
- Improved CTS application + repository documentation based on recommendations

MEK

- Certification support provider
- Participated on support meetings with three individual repositories
- Reviewed certification applications
- Worked with a expert with strong experience of CTS certification process

Lesson learner by Liisi

- EOSC Nordic team - better understanding of CTS requirements
- Improvements on our insufficient documentation
- Improvements on metadata
- CTS not good for general repository
- Biggest obstacles: designated communities
- Recommendations: clear sample materials, questionnaires
- Failure is an option :)

Lesson learner by MEK

- Working with experienced Core Trust Seal expert was unique opportunity to learn by doing.
- In the beginning I was almost useless, in the end I was able to give feedback about a CTS application => I'm ready to help other repositories with certification application process,
- Certification guidelines were fuzzy and difficult to understand in the beginning, those made understandable only after discussion.
 - Most guidelines about complicated subject are not enough, you should provide training & support to clarify guides,

Conclusions

- Working with the data repository service providers was eye-opening.
- The work is often underrated & ill resourced.
- There are a lot of commitment, good will and expertise involved.
- All the help we were able to offer, was gratefully received.

Thank you